

Defining Manifold with Non-convergence: Infinity between Upper and Lower Integral 다양체를 비수렴성으로 정의하기 : 상적분과 하적분 사이 무한

윤지현(Jihyeon Yoon)
somehowme@gmail.com, flyingtext@nate.com
(Amateur Mathematician, Shinhwa Geriatric Hospital)

2024. 7. 14

Abstract

[한글] 상적분과 하적분의 불일치를 통해 일반적인 다양체를 정의할 수 있다. 이를 통해 다양체의 구멍의 개수를 효과적으로 파악할 수 있다.

[English] Manifolds can be defined with non-convergence between upper and lower integral. And with this occasion, hole in the manifolds can be effectively inspected.

1 Introduction

(All the notations and pre-definitions follow the referenced book[김성기(2011)].) It is well-known that integral is defined as follows with arbitrary $\epsilon > 0$:

$$0 \leq \overline{\int_a^b f} - \underline{\int_a^b f} < \epsilon$$

With occasions that are not true with upper and lower integral, sequence of cardinality can be defined.

2 Non-convergence as a Manifold

2.1 Single Variate Function

With $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Assuming that } \overline{\int_a^b f} - \underline{\int_a^b f} > \epsilon &\implies \overline{\int_a^b f} - \underline{\int_a^b f} < \epsilon \\ &\implies \text{card } \epsilon = \aleph_1 \quad (\because \epsilon \in \mathbb{R}) \end{aligned}$$

With expanding a, b to arbitrary intervals:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\forall a, \forall b} \overline{\int_a^b f} - \underline{\int_a^b f} &= n(\forall a, \forall b) \cdot \epsilon \\ \implies \text{card } n(\forall a, \forall b) &= \aleph_0 \quad (\because \text{intervals are countable}), \\ n(\forall a, \forall b) \cdot \epsilon &= \text{card } \mathbb{R} = \aleph_1 \end{aligned}$$

This implies upper sum and lower sum countable stays countable \aleph_0 while extending its projection to ω . With this occasion, minimum definition of edge and vertex can be derived.

Definition 1 (Edge) Edges are discontinuous points in shortest intervals when $n(a, b) = \min n(a, b)$.

Definition 2 (Vertex) Vertices are discontinuous intervals in shortest between edges when $n(a, b) = \min n(a, b)$.

2.2 Extension to Multivariate Function

Assuming multivariate function is $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^\nu$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Assuming that } \overline{\int \cdots \int_a^b d^\nu f} - \int \cdots \int_a^b d^\nu f > \epsilon &\implies \int \cdots \int_a^b d^\nu f - \overline{\int \cdots \int_a^b d^\nu f} < \epsilon \\ &\implies \text{Assuming axiom of choice, card } \epsilon = \aleph_\nu \ (\cdot \cdot \epsilon \in \mathbb{R}) \end{aligned}$$

As corollary, any topological vector manifold has cardinality as much as dimensionality. With this occasion, minimum definition of face can be derived.

Definition 3 (*Face*) Faces are complemetaries to vertex which are discontinous to any boundaries when $n(a, b) = \min n(a, b)$.

Now we can say that straw has one hole safely.

References

[김성기(2011)] 계승혁 김성기, 김도한. 해석개론(개정판 2판). September 2011.